

Object tracking in a stereo and infrared vision system

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Abstract

In this paper, we deal with the problem of real-time detection, recognition and tracking of moving objects in open and unknown environments using an infrared (IR) and visible vision system. A thermo-camera and two stereo visible-cameras synchronized are used to acquire multi-source information: three-dimensional data about *target* geometry and its thermal information are combined to improve the robustness of the tracking procedure. Firstly, target detection is performed by extracting its characteristic features from the images and then by storing the computed parameters on a specific database; secondly, the tracking task is carried on using two different computational approaches. A Hierarchical Artificial Neural Network (HANN) is used during active tracking for the recognition of the actual target, while, when partial occlusions or masking occur, a database retrieval method is used to support the search of the correct target followed. A prototype has been tested on case studies regarding the identification and tracking of animals moving at night in an open environment, and the surveillance of known scenes for unauthorized access control.

1. Introduction

Recognizing and tracking moving objects in video sequences is generally a very challenging task and automatic tools to identify and follow an object – *target* – are often subject to constraints regarding the environment under investigation, the characteristics of the target itself and its full visibility with respect to the background.

Current approaches regarding real-time object tracking are based on (i) successive frame differences [1,2], using also adaptive threshold techniques [3], (ii) trajectory tracking, using weak perspective and optical flow [4], (iii) region approaches, using active contours of the target and neural networks for movement analysis [5], or motion detection and successive regions segmentation [6,7]. In recent years, thanks to the improvement of infrared (IR) technology and the drop of its cost, also thermal infrared imagery has been widely used in tracking applications [8–10]. Besides, the fusion of visible and infrared imagery is start-

ing to be explored as a way to improve the tracking performance [11,12].

In this paper, the problem of moving target detection and tracking is faced by processing multi-source information acquired using a vision system capable of stereo and IR vision. Combining the two acquisition modalities assures different advantages consisting, first of all, of an improvement of target detection capability and robustness, guaranteed by the strength of both media as complementary vision modalities. Infrared vision is a fundamental aid when low-lighting conditions occur or the target has similar colour to the background. Moreover, as a detection of the thermal radiation of the target, the IR information can be manageably acquired on a 24-h basis, under suitable conditions. On the other hand, the visible imagery has a higher resolution and can supply more detailed information about target geometry and localization with respect to the background.

The acquired multi-source information is firstly elaborated for detecting and extracting the target in the current frame of the video sequence. Then, the tracking task is carried on using two different computational approaches. A

Hierarchical Artificial Neural Network (HANN) is used during active tracking for the recognition of the actual target; while, when the target is lost or occluded, a content-based retrieval (CBR) paradigm is applied on an a priori defined database to re-localize the correct target.

In the following sections, we describe our approach, demonstrating its effectiveness in two real case studies: the monitoring of animal movements during the night in an open environment (i.e. natural reserves or parks), and the surveillance of known scenes for unauthorized access control [13].

2. Problem formulation

We face the problem of tracking a moving target distinguishable from a surrounding environment owing to a difference of temperature. In particular, we consider to overcome lighting and environmental condition variation using IR sensors.

The tracking problem in a video sequence consists of two correlated phases: *target spatial localization*, for individuating the target in the current frame, and *target recognition*, for determining whether the identified target is the one to be followed.

Spatial localization can be sub-divided into *detection* and *characterization*; while recognition is performed for an *active tracking* of the target, frame by frame, or for re-localizing it, by means of an *automatic target search* procedure.

The initialization step is performed by manual intervention to allow the operator selecting the right target. For improving the recognition performance and its effectiveness, the user also selects a pre-defined *semantic class* which is associated to the current target. Then, an automatic motion detection procedure is performed to localize the target, and then to extract it from the scene by a rough segmentation.

Once segmented, the target is described through a set of meaningful multi-modal features, belonging to *morphological*, *geometric* and *thermographic* classes, computed to obtain useful information on shape and thermal properties.

To cope with the uncertainty of the localization, increased by partial occlusions or masking, an HANN can be designed to process the set of features during an active tracking procedure, in order to recognize the correctness of the detected target.

In case the HANN does not recognize the target, a wrong object recognition should happen, due to either a masking, partial occlusion of the object in the scene, or a quick movement in an unexpected direction. In this circumstance, the localization of the target is performed, starting from the successive frame, by an automatic search supported by the CBR on a reference database. In this process, only a limited number of frames is considered and, if problems arise, the control is given back to the user.

The general algorithm implementing the above described approach is shown in Fig. 1 and it regards its

Fig. 1. The automatic target tracking algorithm (on-line processing).

on-line processing. In this case, the system is used in real time to perform the tracking task. Extracted features from the selected target drive active tracking with HANN and support the CBR to resolve the queries to the database in case of lost target. Before this stage, an off-line phase is necessary, where known and selected examples are presented to the system so that the neural network can be trained, and all the extracted multi-modal features can be stored in the database, which is organised on the basis of the defined semantic classes. For each defined target class, possible variations of the initial shape are also recorded, for taking into account that the target could be still partially masked or have a different orientation.

More details of the algorithm are described in the following.

3. Target spatial localization

3.1. Target detection

When the tracking procedure is started, the user chooses the target to follow by selecting a reference point, called *centroid* C_0 , internal to it. This point is used in the successive steps, during the automatic detection, to represent the target. In particular, starting from C_0 , a motion prediction algorithm has been defined to localize the target centroid in each frame of the video sequence. According to previous movements of the target, the current expected position is individuated, and then refined through a neighbourhood search, performed on the basis of temperature similarity criteria.

Let us consider the IR image sequence $\{F_i\}_{i=0,1,2,\dots}$, corresponding to the set of frames of a video, where $F_i(p)$ is the thermal value associated to the p th *pixel* in the i th frame. The trajectory followed by the target, till the i th frame, $i > 0$, can be represented as the centroids succession $\{C_j\}_{j=0,\dots,i-1}$. The motion prediction algorithm for determining the centroid C_i in the current frame can be described as shown in Fig. 2.

The coordinate of centroids referring to the last s seconds ($s < 2$ s, s dependent on the semantic class) are interpolated for detecting the expected position P_i^1 . Then, in a circular neighbourhood of P_i^1 of radius equal to the average movement amplitude, an additional point P_i^2 is detected as the point having the maximum similarity with the centroid C_{i-1} of the previous frame. If $\|P_i^2 - P_i^1\| > \sigma$, then a new point P_i^3 is calculated as a linear combination of the previous determined ones. Finally, a local maximum search is again performed in the neighbourhood of P_i^3 to make sure that it is internal to a valid object. This search finds the point C_i that has the thermal level closest to the one of C_{i-1} :

Starting from the current centroid C_i , an automated edge segmentation of the target is performed, using a gradient descent along 16 directions, starting from C_i . Fig. 3 shows a sketch of the segmentation procedure and an example of its result.

Fig. 2. The motion prediction algorithm. The function INTERPOLATE performs the piecewise interpolation of the input points and returns the position of the next point of the succession. Input parameters: i = current frame index; $\{F_i\}_{i=0,1,2,\dots}$ = frames sequence; s = time period in seconds; fps = frames per second; τ = threshold distance; $\|\cdot\|$ = Euclidean distance between two centroids; σ = threshold distance of a candidate centroid; α, β ($\alpha + \beta = 1$) = weights assigned to the points, empirically defined and adjustable by the user.

Fig. 3. (left) The gradient descent procedure finding the edge points starting from the centroid (for sake of clearness, only eight of the 16 points are drawn); (right) example of extracted contour and its marked centroid.

3.2. Target characterization

Once the target has been segmented, multi-source information is extracted in order to obtain a target description. This is made through a feature extraction process performed on the three different images available for each frame in the sequence. In particular, the extraction of a

depth index from the grey level stereo images, performed by computing disparity of the corresponding stereo points, is realized in order to have significant information about the target spatial localization in the 3D scene and the target movement along depth direction, which is useful for the determination of a possible static or dynamic occlusion of the target itself in the observed scene.

Other features consisting in radiometric parameters measuring the temperature and visual features are extracted from the IR images. There are three different groups of visual features which are extracted from the region enclosed by the target contour:

- *Morphological*: shape contour descriptors;
- *Geometric*: perimeter and area measure;
- *Thermographic*: average temperature, its standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, and entropy.

The *semantic class* the target belongs to (i.e. a small, a medium or a large animal,...) can be considered as an additional feature and is chosen by the user among a pre-defined set of possible choices and assigned to the target in the previous phase.

All the extracted information is passed to the recognition phase, in order to assess if the localized target is correct.

4. Target recognition

4.1. Active tracking through HANN

The target recognition procedure is realised using a hierarchical architecture of neural networks. In particular, the architecture is composed of two independent network levels each using a specific network typology that can be trained separately.

The first level focuses on clustering the different features extracted from the segmented target; the second level performs the final recognition, on the basis of the results of the previous one. The architecture is shown in Fig. 4.

The *clustering level* is composed of a set of classifiers, each corresponding to one of the aforementioned classes of features. These classifiers are based on unsupervised *Self Organizing Maps* (SOM) [14] and the training is performed to cluster the input features into classes representative of the possible target semantic classes. At the end of the training, each network is able to classify the values of the specific feature set. The output of the clustering level is an *m-dimensional* vector consisting of the concatenation of the *m* SOMs outputs (in our case $m = 3$). This vector represents the input of the second level.

The *recognition level* consists of a neural network classifier based on Error Back-Propagation (EBP) [15]. Once trained, such network is able to recognize the semantic class that can be associated to the examined target. If the semantic class is correct, as specified by the user, the detected target is recognized and the procedure goes on

Fig. 4. Architecture of the Hierarchical Artificial Neural Network (HANN).

with the active tracking. Otherwise, a wrong target recognition occurs and the automatic target search is applied to the successive frame, in order to find the correct target.

4.2. Automatic target search supported by CBR paradigm

When a wrong target recognition occurs, due to masking or occlusion, or quick movements in an unexpected direction, the automatic target search starts.

The multi-modal features of the candidate target are compared to the ones recorded in a reference database. A similarity function is applied for each feature class [16]. In particular, we considered *colour matching*, using percentages and colour values, and *shape matching*, using the cross-correlation criterion. In order to obtain a global similarity measure, each similarity percentage is associated to a pre-selected weight, using the reference semantic class as a filter to access the database information.

The features of the candidate target are extracted from a new candidate centroid, which is computed starting from the last valid one (C_v). From C_v , considering the trajectory of the target, the same algorithm as in the target detection step is applied so that a candidate centroid C_i in the current frame is found and a candidate target is segmented.

With respect to the actual feature vector, if the most similar pattern found in the database has a similarity degree higher than a prefixed threshold, then the automatic search has success and the target tracking for the next frame is performed through the active tracking. Otherwise in the next frame the automatic search is performed again, still considering the last valid centroid C_v as a starting point.

If after j frames the correct target has not yet been grabbed, the control is given back to the user. The value of j is computed considering the Euclidean distance between C_v and the border point of the frame B_r , along the search direction r , divided by the average velocity Vel of the target previously measured in the last v frames $\{C_j\}_{j=0,\dots,v}$ (Eqs. (1) and (2)):

$$j = \|C_v - B_r\| / \text{Vel} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Vel} = \left(\sum_{i=0}^{v-1} \|C_i - C_{i+1}\| \right) / v \quad (2)$$

5. Results

The method implemented has been applied to real case studies: (i) to track animal movements in an open environment during the night, for the fauna monitoring in natural parks, and (ii) for video surveillance to control unauthorized access in restricted access areas.

Due to the nature of the targets to which the tracking has been applied, using IR technology is fundamental. The temperature that characterizes living beings has been exploited to enhance the contrast of significant targets with respect to a surrounding background.

The videos were acquired using a thermo-camera in the 8–12 μm wavelength range, mounted on a moving structure covering 360° pan and 90° tilt, and equipped with 12° and 24° optics to have 320 × 240 pixel spatial resolution.

Both the thermo-camera and the two stereo visible-cameras were positioned in order to explore a scene 100 m far, sufficient in our experimental cases. The frame acquisition rate was 25 fps.

In the fauna monitoring experimental case, during the off-line stage, the database was built taking into account different image sequences relative to different classes of the monitored animals. In particular, three main semantic classes were determined: the *large-animal* class counting all the monitored animals of a large size like deer, the *medium-animal* class including animals of medium size like boars, and the *small-animal* class considering other kind

of animals like rabbits or badgers. For each outlined semantic class, different positions were considered. In more details, four different positions for boars, rabbits and other small animals and six for deer were registered.

The number of operations performed for each frame when tracking animals of medium size consists of about 500,000 operations for the identification and characterization phases, while the active tracking requires about 4000 operations. This assures the real-time functioning of the procedure on a personal computer of medium power. The automatic search process can require a higher number of operations, but it is performed when the target is partially occluded or lost due to some obstacles, so it can be reasonable to spend more time in finding it, thus losing some frames. Of course, the number of operations depends on the dimension of the animal to be followed, i.e. bigger targets require a higher effort to be segmented and characterized.

An example of target tracking is shown in Fig. 5; while Figs. 6 and 7 illustrate a plot of the centroids trajectory for

Fig. 6. Centroids trajectory for the tracking fragment of Fig. 5: superposition of the centroids and the extracted contours of the target with respect to the (x, y) reference system of the frame.

Fig. 5. Example of deer tracking: eight frames, distant 0.75 s each other, corresponding to a monitoring time of 6 s.

Fig. 7. Behaviour of average velocity (V_m) and displacement (ΔS) functions (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 8. Example of surveillance in case of intrusion.

the same tracking example and of the average velocity and displacement, respectively.

In the video-surveillance case, the *human* class has been composed taking into account six different postures (e.g. upstanding, crouched, crawling) for three different people typologies (short, middle, tall).

The acquired images are pre-processed to reduce the noise. An example of target segmentation is shown in Fig. 8.

6. Conclusion

A methodology has been proposed for detection and tracking of moving targets in real-time video sequences acquired with two stereo visible cameras and an IR camera mounted on a robotized system.

Target recognition during active tracking has been performed, using an optimized *Hierarchical Artificial Neural Network* (HANN). The HANN system has a modular architecture which allows the introduction of new sets of features including new information useful for a more accurate recognition. The introduction of new features does not influence the training of the other SOM classifiers and only requires small changes in the recognition level. The modular architecture allows the reduction of local complexity and at the same time, to implement a flexible system.

In case of automatic searching of a masked or occluded target, a *Content-Based Retrieval* paradigm has been used for the retrieval and comparison of the currently extracted features with the previously stored in a reference database.

The achieved results are promising for further improvements as the introduction of additional new characterizing features and enhancement of hardware requirements for a quick response to rapid movements of the targets.

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